

THERMALLY CONDUCTIVE FIBER-REINFORCED COMPOSITE MATERIALS

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ABSTRACT

The capability of existing polymer-based composite materials in heat transfer by conduction is limited. In this study it is demonstrated that the thermal conductivities of polymeric fiber-reinforced materials can be enhanced by using coated fibers and by adding thermally conductive microspheres to the resin. The rationale is to increase the intensity of the heat flow both in fibers and the matrix, simultaneously. A two-dimensional model based on the flash pulse method is implemented to estimate the thermal conductivities of material systems consist of polymer matrix, metal-coated fibers and metal-coated microspheres. The performance of the model is assessed through digital simulation studies by employing the finite element method. It is found that the thermal conductivities in the longitudinal and the transverse directions are highly dependent on the fiber and microspheres volume fractions as well as the thermal conductivities of fiber, matrix, microspheres and coatings.

1. INTRODUCTION

Polymer matrix composite materials inherently have low thermal conductivities (TC). This is regarded as one of their advantages over conventional metallic materials for thermal insulation purposes [1,2]. However, for those applications in which lightweight, high stiffness, and high heat flow rate capabilities are important, such

as in many electrical systems, composite materials with high TC are required. Thermal conductivities of more than 294 W/m⁰K (in-plane) and 90 W/m⁰K (through-the-thickness) have not been reported in the open literature for existing *metal matrix* composites [3]. Due to polymers' low TC (e.g., $k_{\text{epoxy}}=0.24$ W/m⁰K), polymeric composites by far have much lower TC than those of metal matrix composite materials. This is an important issue when one is concerned with the problem of heat transfer in electrical systems such as enclosures of transformers and circuit breakers, transmissions towers and poles, electronic enclosures, etc. The relatively low TC of polymer-based composites results in the accumulation of wasted energy, and consequent increase in the temperature of the system. This, in turn, increases the degradation of the system's reliability and electrical performance life. In addition, polymeric composites with a very high thermal conductivity are excellent candidates to replace glass heat exchangers in chemical plants, and potting compounds (for protection of electronic devices from dust and moisture) in the automobile industry. Furthermore, such materials are highly desirable for EMI shielding, lightning strike and high temperature applications.

Metallic coated pitch fibers are the prime candidate for fiber reinforced material systems with high thermal conductivities. This combination offers light weight and high structural reinforcement of graphite fibers with the high thermal and electrical conductivities of metals such as Nickle or Copper. Although, pitch fibers have even higher TC than metals the metallic coating is needed to prevent bunching of the fibers. In addition, fiber coating greatly enhances the reliability of the structures such as transformers, circuit breakers, towers and poles, in withstanding direct lightning strikes by an efficient electrical continuity for ground path. Fiber coating also provides excellent EMI shielding for structures.

The inclusion of coated microspheres in the matrix has a significant effect on the intensity of heat transfer through the material. The overall thermal conductivity of the microspheres depends on their core and coating material properties. Microspheres are very small particles which are commercially available in solid or hollow forms. The density of a microsphere is approximately one-fifth of most resins and its diameter

is 50-100 times smaller than fibres. Therefore, when added to the resin, not only can they increase the thermal conductivity, they also can contribute to weight reduction, dimensional stability, and even rigidity and stress resistance of the matrix.

2. BACKGROUND

There are more than one hundred theoretical and empirical models available which can be used to predict the TC of composites [4]. It has been shown that among all models the one by Nielsen [5,6] is the most accurate over the widest range of parameters [7]. However, neither Nielsen's nor the other models consider fiber coating, and the contact resistance between the fiber and the matrix. In recent analytical studies fiber coating has been included [8-10]. Effects of micro-cracking in the matrix and interfacial thermal contact resistance on TC have been addressed by Hasselman and co-workers [11,13].

The problem of heat transfer in fibrous composites has not been well explored. Only a very limited number of research work have addressed the transient heat conduction in composites. Wang et al [14-16] performed macroscopic studies of the residual thermal stresses in an elastic, orthotropic medium subject to a sudden change in the temperature. At the microscopic level, Numura and Chou [17] addressed the problem of heat conduction in an infinite medium composed of infinite number of fibers due to an oscillating temperature field. Numura and Haji-Sheikh [18] extended this work to the transient heat conduction in a finite region with a finite number of fibers by using the Galerkin method. They demonstrated that the overall thermal conductivity is a nonlinear function of thermal conductivities of the matrix and fibers, and that, the simple linear rule of mixture is not valid.

Experimental methods for measuring thermal conductivity can be classified into two main groups: methods based on steady state heat transfer, and techniques which utilize time dependent temperature field. These methods have been well documented or referred to in a number of publications including Toulouian et al [19]. The "guarded hot plate" method [20] is a steady state technique in which the specimen is heated by a hot metal platen attached to it. The temperature is measured at the interfaces to

estimate the thermal conductivity. The three major problems with this method are: the heat loss from the specimen edge, the contact resistance of sample-platen interface, and the time required to obtain the steady state temperature distribution. These problems have been addressed and some improvements have been suggested [21,22].

The "hot wire" method is a transient method of measuring thermal conductivity [23-28]. This method consists of embedding a wire in the center of a brick shape piece of the material, and applying a step flux to the wire. The thermal conductivity of the material is determined from the temperature history of the wire. The resulting expression for temperature excess in the wire (source $q(t)$) which is surrounded by an infinite medium is given by [29]

$$\bar{\theta} = \frac{1}{4\pi k} \int_0^t \frac{q(t') e^{-r^2/4\alpha(t-t')}}{(t-t')} dt' \quad (1)$$

where $\bar{\theta} = T - T_{initial}$ and t is time. For a constant line source $q(t') = q_0$, and small r , Eq. (1) reduces to

$$k = \frac{q_0 \ln(t_2/t_1)}{4\pi (\bar{\theta}_2 - \bar{\theta}_1)} \quad (2)$$

Only the knowledge of temperature at a single location (the heat source) is required to compute or measure the thermal conductivity. For materials with relatively low conductivity the effect of a heat source should not be felt far from the source for a reasonably long times. Therefore, a finite amount of the material can be treated as an infinite medium. Some of the advantages of this method over the guarded hot plate method are: the hot wire technique dose not require a control system, the data are taken in a relatively short time span, and the geometry can be relatively small so that data are more readily determined. The difficulties associated with this method are specimen preparation and thermocouple placement. In addition, biaxial TC measurement for anisotropic materials is not possible.

The "flash pulse" method [30] is also a transient method of measuring thermal conductivity which was first described by Parker et al [31]. Since with this method

very accurate data in a short period of time (of order of seconds) can be obtained, presently this technique has a dominant position in the field. In this method, one face of relatively small (of the order of mm) penny-shape specimen is subjected to a very high flux of radiant energy in a very short time period (of the order of msec). By measuring the temperature on the other face of the sample thermal diffusivity and consequently the thermal conductivity can be determined. The three sources of non-measurement errors: the finite pulse-time effect, heat losses or gains, and nonuniform heating have been well addressed [32-38]. It has been found that it is possible to measure the TC of fine fibers [39], laminated composites [40-45], and fiber reinforced composite materials [46-49] with this method. It has also been shown that the biaxial TC measurement can be performed by the flash pulse method [50].

3. UNIT CELL MODELING

Let us consider a unit cell of the material which consists of fiber, fiber's coating, bonding interface, microsphere and microsphere's coating as shown in Figure 1. Due to the symmetry with respect to the x -axis it is necessary to analyze only one half of the cell. A heat flux is applied to the front face of the unit cell in a very short period of time. Except the front face, the other sides are considered to be isolated and the surrounding environment is assumed to be a vacuum. This is done to prevent the heat transfer by convection and radiation. The in-plane axial and transverse TC are determined by considering two different set of boundary conditions which are shown schematically in Figures 1 and 2.

The Taylor-Cape modified method is considered to obtain the TC of the unit cell [51]. This is done to account for the correction necessary for the cases where the ratio of $\tau/t_{1/2}$ is greater than 0.02, where τ is the pulse time and $t_{1/2}$ is the time required for the rare face temperature to reach half-maximum. The modified relation for thermal diffusivity is given by

$$\alpha = \frac{\alpha^2}{\pi^2 t_c} \quad (3)$$

where α is the thermal diffusivity, a is the thickness of the cell, and t_c is the characteristic time. Based on a graph presented in Ref. [51], the following relation, for a step pulse heat flux, can be developed to calculate the characteristic time

$$t_c = 0.742t_{1/2} - 0.422\tau \quad (4)$$

$t_{1/2}$ is computed by a transient heat transfer finite element analysis. The composite thermal conductivity is obtained by

$$k = \rho c_p \alpha \quad (5)$$

where ρ is the density and c_p is the specific heat at constant pressure. The density and the specific heat of the composite is predicted based on rule of mixture.

4. NUMERICAL RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In this work, a two-dimensional finite element model of a unit cell of a material which consists of coated fibers and coated microspheres is developed. This model is based on the flash pulse method. A mesh of 1224 linear quadrilateral and triangular elements was used to predict the transient temperature field of the unit cell under a sudden step pulse heat flux. The number of elements are sufficient to satisfy the convergence. This was checked by examining several mesh patterns.

In all the numerical results presented, the initial temperature of the unit cell, T_i , is 20°C and a step pulse heat flux of 6.64×10^{-3} cal-gr/sec-mm² in a 1 msec period is applied to the boundary of the unit cell as shown in Figures 1 and 2. Also, the following properties are considered:

$$\frac{\rho_f}{\rho_m} = 1.9; \quad \frac{\rho_{fc}}{\rho_m} = 3.0; \quad \frac{\rho_{fc}}{\rho_m} = 3.0; \quad \frac{\rho_{ic}}{\rho_m} = 7.8$$

$$\frac{c_f}{c_m} = 0.5; \quad \frac{c_{fc}}{c_m} = 0.3; \quad \frac{c_i}{c_m} = 0.5; \quad \frac{c_{ic}}{c_m} = 0.2$$

where subscripts f , m , fc , i and ic represent, respectively, fiber, matrix, fiber coating, inclusion, and inclusion's coating. In the following, the performance of the model has

been assessed through digital simulation studies by examining the effects of system parameters.

The axial composite thermal conductivity (CTC) is highly dependent on the TC of fibers. The effects of the fiber and fiber's coating TC on the axial CTC are presented in Figure 3. It can be seen that for fiber-to-matrix TC ratios of more than 100 the axial CTC does not change, considerably. The CTC in the transverse direction is not affected as much as in the axial direction. This is illustrated in Figure 3 in which the ratios of both the TC of the fiber and fiber's coating with respect to the TC of the matrix vary from 1 to 1000. This demonstrates the degree of the dependency of the CTC to the material orthotropy, and that, the thermal conductivity in fibrous composites is highly directional.

The axial and transverse CTC vary nonlinearly with fiber volume fraction as shown in Figures 5 and 6. The effect of fiber volume fraction is minimal for fiber-to-matrix TC ratios of more than 100. As expected, the CTC is affected more in the axial direction than in the transverse direction by increasing the fiber volume fraction. Figures 7 and 8 demonstrate the effect of fiber's coating on the CTC. By comparing these Figures it can be concluded that the effect of fiber's coating volume fraction on the axial CTC of the composite is more pronounced than those of the transverse direction. It is interesting to note that the effect of coating-to-matrix TC ratios of more than 100 on both the axial and transverse TC of composites is minimal.

The effect of bonding material between the fiber's coating and matrix on the CTC is presented in Figures 9 and 10. For a wide range of bonding-to-matrix ratios the axial CTC is increased by increasing the bonding volume fraction as shown in Figure 9. However, the transverse CTC is enhanced only when the bonding-to-matrix TC ratio is more than one, and decreases for all the ratios less than one by increasing the bonding volume fraction.

Addition of the coated microspheres to the matrix have a considerable effect on the axial and transverse CTC. This can be seen by examining Figures 11 and 12 where both the inclusion's volume fraction and the inclusions' coating-to-matrix TC ratio have equally significant effects on the CTC. It is noticed that the effect of the

inclusions' coating-to-matrix TC ratios of more than 100 on the transverse composite TC is minimal.

5. CONCLUSIONS

This study demonstrates that the directional TC in polymeric fiber reinforced composites can be greatly enhanced by embedding coated fibers in the matrix and mixing the resin with coated microspheres. Based on the flash pulse method a finite element model was developed to analyze the TC of a unit cell of the material. It is shown that the addition of microsphere to the matrix and fiber volume fraction have considerable effect on the TC of fibrous composites. It is also concluded that the coating of fibers and microspheres are important factors in increasing the composite thermal conductivities in both longitudinal and transverse directions.

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Figure 1. Geometric configuration of the unit cell used to study the axial composite thermal conductivity.

Figure 2. Geometric configuration of the unit cell used to study the transverse composite thermal conductivity.

Figure 3. Effects of fiber and fiber's coating thermal conductivities on the axial composite thermal conductivity.

Figure 4. Effects of fiber and fiber's coating thermal conductivities on the Transverse composite thermal conductivity.

Figure 5. Effects of fiber volume fraction and fiber thermal conductivity on the axial composite thermal conductivity.

Figure 6. Effects of fiber volume fraction and fiber thermal conductivity on the transverse composite thermal conductivity.

Figure 7. Effects of fiber's coating volume fraction and thermal conductivity on the axial composite thermal conductivity.

Figure 8. Effects of fiber's coating volume fraction and thermal conductivity on the transverse composite thermal conductivity.

Figure 9. Effects of fiber's bonding volume fraction and thermal conductivity on the axial composite thermal conductivity.

Figure 10. Effects of fiber's bonding volume fraction and thermal conductivity on the transverse composite thermal conductivity.

Figure 11. Effects of inclusion's volume fraction and thermal conductivity on the axial composite thermal conductivity.

Figure 12. Effects of inclusion's volume fraction and thermal conductivity on the transverse composite thermal conductivity.